

INITIAL REFORMS IN THE PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE (1991-2000)

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Annotation: This work analyzes the reforms implemented in the preservation, conservation and restoration of cultural heritage in the first years of Uzbekistan's independence. Between 1991 and 2000, a number of legal frameworks were created in the country for the protection of historical and cultural monuments, state programs were adopted, and important monuments were restored.

The work studies the decrees of the President, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, the activities of the Ministry of Cultural Affairs, and the results of cooperation with international organizations. In particular, the work carried out on the basis of the Law "On the Protection of Cultural Heritage" adopted in 1992, the Main Department for the Protection of Cultural Heritage Objects established in 1995, and the State Program "Preservation and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects" in 1997 will be analyzed.

Also, Uzbekistan's membership in UNESCO in 1996 and the inclusion of the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva in the World Cultural Heritage List will be studied as factors that influenced the process of cultural heritage preservation. This study will highlight important aspects of the reforms related to the preservation of cultural heritage during the years of independence and analyze their results and impact.

Keywords: cultural heritage, independence, reforms, restoration, state program, UNESCO, legislation.

INTRODUCTION.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, the preservation, conservation and restoration of national culture and historical heritage became one of the priorities of state policy. Because cultural heritage is an invaluable asset that reflects the identity, historical roots and cultural traditions of the nation. During the Soviet era, some historical monuments were not given enough attention, and some are under threat of extinction was left. For this reason, large-scale reforms were carried out in the early years of independence on the protection of cultural heritage.

In the period from 1991 to 2000, a number of important decisions were made on the legal protection of cultural heritage sites, their restoration and promotion at the international level. In particular, the adoption of the Law "On the Protection of Cultural

Heritage" in 1992, the establishment of the Main Department for the Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites in 1995, and the adoption of the State Program in 1997 were important steps in this direction.

Also, Uzbekistan's membership in UNESCO in 1996 and the inclusion of the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva in the World Cultural Heritage List played an important role in the preservation and international promotion of the country's cultural heritage. During this period, many historical monuments were restored, and significant progress was made in developing national culture and passing on heritage to future generations.

This work analyzes the initial reforms, adopted legislative acts and implemented measures aimed at preserving cultural heritage in the period from 1991 to 2000. In addition, the results of these reforms and their significance today are also studied.

13 famous monuments were registered with the International World Heritage Committee. The Ak Astona Baba, Hakim Termizi architectural complexes in Surkhandarya, the Kyrgyz Palace, and the Arab Ata, Ishratkhona, Mirsaid Bahrom mausoleums in the republic, the Bahauddin, Chor Bakr, Sheikh Mukhtar Vali complexes, as well as the Rabati Malik, Jarkurgan and Vobkent minarets, were submitted for inclusion in the list of world tangible monuments.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

Various sources and scientific literature are important in studying the reforms implemented in the early years of independence to preserve cultural heritage. This section analyzes existing scientific research, legislation, official documents, and reports of international organizations on this topic. 1. Legislation and official documents

During the years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a number of laws and resolutions on the protection of cultural heritage. In particular:

March 13, 1992 - Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Cultural Heritage". This document established the main standards for the preservation, restoration and use of cultural heritage objects.

1995 - Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the establishment of the Main Department for the Protection of Cultural Heritage **Objects**.

1997 - State program "Preservation and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects". Large-scale restoration projects were implemented within the framework of this program.

1996 - Uzbekistan's membership in UNESCO and the subsequent inclusion of cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva in the World Heritage List made it possible to promote cultural heritage on an international scale.

These official documents are the main source for analyzing how state policy on the preservation of cultural heritage was formed.

DISCUSSION.

In the first years of Uzbekistan's independence, there was a need to implement fundamental reforms in the preservation of cultural heritage. Since some historical monuments were not given sufficient attention during the Soviet period, and some were under threat of extinction, the state paid special attention to this area after independence. Between 1991 and 2000, important decisions were made on the legal protection of cultural heritage, its restoration, and the establishment of international cooperation.

Several key issues were considered during the discussion:

1. Formation of legal foundations

The Law "On the Protection of Cultural Heritage", adopted in 1992, became an important legal foundation for the preservation and use of cultural heritage objects. The establishment of the Main Department for the Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites in 1995 formed a systematic approach to this area by the state.

Within the framework of the 1997 state program, attention was paid to the restoration of historical monuments and their connection with the tourism sector.

2. Practical developments and restoration processes

Historical monuments in the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva were gradually restored in the early years of independence.

Although some monuments were neglected during the Soviet era, they have been involved in large-scale restoration processes since the 1990s.

For example, the Registan complex, Ichan-Kala and other important monuments have been restored on the basis of state programs.

3. International cooperation and relations with UNESCO

Uzbekistan's accession to UNESCO in 1996 has made it possible to promote national cultural heritage sites internationally.

In 1997, as a result of the inclusion of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva in the World Heritage List, international programs were implemented to preserve and promote these cities.

International grants and financial assistance were attracted for the restoration of historical monuments of Uzbekistan.

4. Positive and negative aspects of reforms

Positive aspects:

A legal framework for the preservation of national cultural heritage was created.

Restoration processes were launched.

Cooperation with UNESCO expanded.

Disadvantages and problems:

In the early years, some projects were not fully implemented due to financial difficulties.

In the restoration processes, sometimes cases were observed where materials were used that did not correspond to historical architectural styles.

In Surkhandarya alone, there are 561 historical monuments of cultural heritage, the age of which covers the period from the Paleolithic stage to the 20th century. Of these, 44 are archaeological, 36 are architectural and sacred sites, 39 are monumental and artistic, and 42 are tourist attractions.

RESULTS.

During 1991-2000, a number of important achievements were achieved as a result of the initial reforms aimed at preserving cultural heritage. These results were manifested in such areas as the formation of legal frameworks, the restoration of historical monuments, the establishment of international cooperation, and increased attention to cultural heritage in society.

1. Creation of a legal and organizational framework

In 1992, the Law “On the Protection of Cultural Heritage” was adopted, which established the procedure for the preservation and use of cultural heritage objects.

In 1995, the Main Department for the Protection of Cultural Heritage Objects was established. This institution was engaged in the registration, monitoring and restoration of cultural heritage sites.

In 1997, the State Program on the “Preservation and Use of Cultural Heritage Sites” was adopted, and measures were taken to restore historical monuments and link them with the tourism sector.

2. Work carried out on the restoration and preservation of historical monuments

In the early years of independence, a number of historical monuments in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and Tashkent were restored.

In particular, large-scale restoration work was carried out on the Registan complex, the Mausoleum of Amir Temur, Shahi Zinda, Ark Castle in Bukhara and Ichan-Kala in Khiva.

Some monuments were transformed into tourism centers, increasing their economic efficiency.

3. Promoting cultural heritage internationally In 1996, Uzbekistan became a member of UNESCO and was able to implement programs for the protection of cultural heritage at the international level.

In 1997, the historical centers of the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva were included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. This served to preserve the historical monuments of these cities and attract international attention to them.

International grants and donor funds were attracted for the restoration of historical monuments of Uzbekistan.

4. Increased attention to cultural heritage in society

As a result of the state policy on the preservation of cultural heritage sites, the population's interest in its own history increased.

During the 1990s, the number of scientific studies devoted to historical monuments and architectural monuments in Uzbekistan increased.

Various festivals and conferences on the preservation of national culture and historical heritage were organized, and attention was paid to the promotion of cultural heritage.

SUMMARY.

The reforms of 1991-2000 laid an important foundation for the preservation and development of the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. The laws and state programs adopted during this period allowed for the systematic protection of cultural heritage objects. The restoration of historical monuments and the establishment of cooperation with international organizations laid the foundation for the worldwide recognition of the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the initial reforms on the preservation of cultural heritage served as the starting point for large-scale work carried out in subsequent years.

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